

Empirical comparisons between global F-test, Scheffe test and multiple contrast test against the total mean

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Abstract

The global ANOVA F-test based on the quadratic test statistics using the sum of squares in the nominator. An alternative to the quadratic test statistic are linear multiple contrast tests, i.e. the multiple contrast for comparing the treatment means with the overall mean (MCT). A certain alternative to the ANOVA F-test is the Scheffe test, however considering any contrasts instead of just pairwise contrasts. Size and power of these three global tests are compared for finite sample sizes by means of a simulation study. Unbalanced designs and heteroscedasticity are considered.

1 Tests

Considering a completely randomized one-way layout with a single factor fa in k levels $y_{ji} = \alpha_j + fa_j + \epsilon_{ij}$ with $\epsilon_{ij} \sim N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$, i.e. a Gaussian error, possibly heteroscedastic in a balanced or unbalanced design. The special case of few levels is considered $k = 3, 4, 5, \text{ or } 6$, quite common in recent designs in therapeutically, pharmacological or toxicological trials or studies.

Here we consider as a standard k -sample test the ANOVA F-test and possible alternatives. According to the inverse Gabriel theorem [1] each multiple comparison procedure can be translated into a global test, simply by the min-p-value approach. Two construction principles can be used for k -sample tests in one-way designs: 1) the sum across quadratic differences to overall mean in the nominator of the F-test, or 2) the maximum test across the linear differences against overall mean [6]. Although both tests are formulated for or $H_1 = \mu_i - \mu_j \exists i \neq j$ (i.e. at least one i , anyone) both tests reveal quite different least favorable configurations of the expected values [5], the latter is used here because it provides both global and elementary decisions (adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals) and is easier to generalize for various scenarios within the framework of generalized linear (mixed) models [4]. For normal distributed and homoscedastic errors in a one-way layout with $i = 1, \dots, k$ treatment groups T_i , the MCT represents a maximum test $t_{MCT} = \max(t_1, \dots, t_\lambda)$ based on a certain class of the single contrast tests:

$$t_{Contrast} = \sum_{i=1}^k \zeta_i \bar{y}_i / S \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k \zeta_i^2 / n_i}.$$

It is based on the common global mean square error estimator S and the global degree of freedom $df = \sum n_i - k$ and is univariate $t_{df, 1-\alpha}$ -distributed under H_0 . The contrast coefficients ζ_i^λ determine the specific kind of MCT. For comparisons against the overall mean exactly $\lambda = k$ contrasts exist, see Table 1 for a simplified balanced design with $k = 5$ as an example: I.e. only k two-sided elementary comparisons are performed, compared with $k(k-1)/2$ all-pairs pairwise comparisons or infinity comparisons for the Scheffe test. Three main global tests are compared: i) F-test (F-test), ii) the multiple contrast vs. total

ζ_i	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	T_5
ζ_1	-1	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
ζ_2	0.25	-1	0.25	0.25	0.25
ζ_3	0.25	0.25	-1	0.25	0.25
ζ_4	0.25	0.25	0.25	-1	0.25
ζ_4	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	-1

Table 1: Overall mean comparisons contrasts for $k = 5$ treatment groups T_i in a balanced design.

mean (MCT) and iii) the global Scheffe test (Scheffe). Additionally, the protected modification against heteroscedasticity are analyzed: i) using the sandwich estimator instead of the common means square error [3] (sMCT) and ii) using Welch-type degree of freedom [2] (wMCT). Clearly, the comparisons against the F-test is unfair for heteroscedastic errors. But it is still performed, to demonstrate its possible problematic properties under real data conditions.

2 Simulations

For a particular unbalanced sample size design ($n_1 = 16, n_i = 8$) for $k = 5$ normal distributed random variable were generated under both H_0 and H_1 under homoscedastic errors and specific heteroscedastic errors. Table 2 shows the estimated sizes and powers for 5000 runs.

Hypoth	Variances	Var.pattern	Expected values	F-test	MCT	sMCT	Scheffe	wMCT
H_0	homog	$\sigma_i = const$	$\mu_i = const$	0.049	0.050	0.070	0.021	0.060
H_0	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_1$	$\mu_i = const$	0.149	0.193	0.062	0.107	0.053
H_0	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_5$	$\mu_i = const$	0.153	0.196	0.063	0.108	0.055
H_0	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_4$	$\mu_i = const$	0.140	0.192	0.059	0.101	0.052
H_1	homog	$\sigma_i = const$	$\mu_1 > \mu_i$	0.894	0.933	0.914	0.740	0.925
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_1$	$\mu_1 > \mu_i$	0.190	0.278	0.218	0.089	0.212
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_5$	$\mu_1 > \mu_i$	0.460	0.493	0.668	0.309	0.658
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_4$	$\mu_1 > \mu_i$	0.437	0.497	0.661	0.300	0.662
H_1	homog	$\sigma_i = const$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 > \mu_i$	0.946	0.849	0.843	0.742	0.832
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_1$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 > \mu_i$	0.181	0.196	0.413	0.081	0.430
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_5$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 > \mu_i$	0.461	0.363	0.591	0.282	0.587
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_4$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 > \mu_i$	0.475	0.373	0.579	0.291	0.570
H_1	homog	$\sigma_i = const$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 > \mu_i$	0.887	0.781	0.757	0.781	0.709
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_1$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 > \mu_i$	0.140	0.116	0.440	0.061	0.454
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_5$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 > \mu_i$	0.421	0.409	0.487	0.292	0.475
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_4$	$\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 > \mu_i$	0.431	0.403	0.489	0.292	0.464
H_1	homog	$\sigma_i = const$	$\mu_1 < \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 < \mu_5$	0.679	0.614	0.598	0.460	0.574
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_1$	$\mu_1 < \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 < \mu_5$	0.332	0.308	0.407	0.307	0.398
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_4$	$\mu_1 < \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 < \mu_5$	0.120	0.148	0.263	0.229	0.265
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_5$	$\mu_1 < \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 < \mu_5$	0.295	0.323	0.269	0.323	0.266
H_1	homog	$\sigma_i = const$	$\mu_1 > \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 > \mu_5$	0.685	0.652	0.630	0.652	0.617
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_1$	$\mu_1 > \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 > \mu_5$	0.110	0.151	0.243	0.151	0.243
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_4$	$\mu_1 > \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 > \mu_5$	0.345	0.329	0.445	0.328	0.425
H_1	hetero	$\uparrow \sigma_5$	$\mu_1 > \mu_2 > \mu_3 > \mu_4 > \mu_5$	0.318	0.334	0.332	0.243	0.335

Table 2: Size and power estimates for an unbalanced design (k=5) and heteroscedasticity

First, all tests control the α level only for homoscedastic errors, whereas F-test, MCT and Scheffe-test reveal an unacceptable inflationary behavior. These tests can not be recommended for general use

in real data studies. Only the protected tests controls the level approximately for such small sample sizes (marked in red). For homogeneous variances the power comparison between F-test and MCT is specific: for $H_1 : \mu_1 \neq \mu_i$ alternatives an advantage for MCT, vice versa. This pattern is lost for heteroscedasticity, even taking the inflationary properties of the F-test: in all considered patterns the power of the modified MCT's is higher (where little differences between both modifications).

3 Summary

Although the F-test is widely used to evaluated one-way layouts, this test can not be recommended for routine use. Under even mild heteroscedasticity it neither controls the size nor reveals high power. Instead the global version of the multiple contrast test against to total mean should be used, modified either by means of sandwich variance estimator or Welch-type degree of freedom.

References

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